

ADVANCING PEDAGOGICAL FOUNDATIONS FOR INFORMATION ANALYTICAL COMPETENCE DEVELOPMENT IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *Global informatization, socio-economic, military-political, commercial, industrial, educational and other spheres in the world, as a result of which information security has become an important part of politics as an integral part of general security. Along with the expansion of relations in the field of informatization, one of the most pressing issues has become a new public attitude aimed at preventing offenses in this area - information security. At the same time, it is important to introduce learning technologies to ensure information security in the practice of teaching in higher education. In particular, the integrated use of best practices (Thomas More University of Applied Sciences - Belgium, Linnaeus University - Sweden, School of Information Risk Management - England) is relevant in the formation of professional competence in the field of information security.*

Therefore, this article analyzes the pedagogical and psychological features, factors of protection of students from the threat of harmful information in the educational process, the mechanisms of interaction of teachers and parents in the formation of information literacy of students. The article also examines the preventive and effective components of the system of protection of students from the threat of harmful information, the problem of developing a critical attitude to foreign information in protecting students from the threat of harmful information. As a result, the issue of proper formation of information security competencies in the younger generation, who are the owners of tomorrow, will be resolved positively.

Keywords: *personality, education, harmful information, information consumption culture.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The country has developed a state policy for informatization of society, created a legal foundation for the development of information resources, information technologies and information systems, as well as the introduction of a national information system in modern conditions, taking into account world principles. In order to strengthen this process, in the "Strategy for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021" improving the issues of increasing information security and information protection, timely and appropriate response to threats in the sphere of information and prevention of information attacks that threaten the consciousness of young people, the formation of a culture of the internet and other information resources among young people [1,39] played an main role. In the Republic of Uzbekistan, a state policy on the informatization of society has been developed, a regulatory and legal framework has been created for the development of information resources, information technologies and information systems, as well as the introduction of a national information system, taking into account the principles of the modern world. In particular, on the improvement and development of information technology and the speed of information (internet): "In today's conditions, the widespread introduction of the most advanced information and communication technologies is a priority. In accordance with the National Program in this area, it is necessary to further develop telecommunication technologies, communication systems and infrastructure, the creation of "electronic government" information systems and a database " [2,15].

In this case, the law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated September 9, 2017 URK-444 "On the protection of children from harmful information to their health," the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 8, 2019 F-5465 "On the protection of children from harmful information to their health" The decision PQ-4307 dated May 3, 2019 "On steps to build a concept for the development of a national idea at a new stage of growth of Uzbekistan" "On additional measures to improve the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work," the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 31, 2019 No1059 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work," the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated March 26, 2021 PQ-5040 "On measures to radically improve the system of spiritual and educational work," the resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan " On the adoption of the idea of continuous spiritual education and measures for its implementation" and the completion of the duties established other rules relating to this activity, instructors were entrusted with a significant deal of responsibility.

It is widely acknowledged that modern society is through a fundamentally distinct stage of development: that of an informed society, or, more broadly, the transition to an information civilization. The development of technology for the generation and distribution of information, in particular, has increased the pace with which information is disseminated.

Direct experience, personal conversation, and other sources of information are all used to obtain the essential information (books, radio, television, magazines, newspapers and other sources in the form of symbols). As a result, the law of social growth is governed by information sources, as well as the dramatic increase and preponderance of information received from direct experience and personal communication..

Researchers G.V.Grachev and I.I.Melnik concur with our viewpoint: "The complexity of social processes in society and the direct impact of social changes on a person's daily life make him more dependent on the flow of media messages. A person receives some information necessary for social behavior and life in society, based on everyday experience. Information influencing socialization can be found in television and radio programs and periodicals"[3,41].

Many experts believe that mass media has an impact on people's daily lives because it creates a "second reality" - "subjective reality" - that has an equal impact as objective reality.

2. METHODS.

The article is based on a comparative-critical study and analysis of political, philosophical, sociological, psychological and pedagogical literature on a generally accepted problem, sociometric methods (questionnaires, interviews, interviews), pedagogical experimental methods.

3.LITERATURE REVIEW

The philosophical and pedagogical aspects of such issues as protecting young people from harmful information flows, information security skills, ideological immunity in our country were studied by Sh. Pakhrudinov, M. Kuronov, Z.Davronov, B.Aliev, S.Otamurotov, A.Ochildiev, I.Khojamurodov, Sh.Kakhkhorova, U. Saidov. In particular, Z.Davronov (Davronov Z. Informatics // Economics and reporting. - Tashkent: 2010. No. 5/6.) noted that as a result of its debut of computers, information technologies penetrate deeply into the development of science, the content and essence of the cognitive process, whereas B.Aliyev, A.Melikulov (Aliiev B., Melikulov A. "Are you aware of information attacks?" - Tashkent: "Ma'naviyat", 2015) noted the purpose of such efforts, which serves the interests of the main driving force of the information process, is to strike a blow at traditional thinking based on national interests and values, and to

establish a single world dominance based on Western standards, in economic, social, political and cultural terms.

Socio-pedagogical, didactic and methodological aspects of the problem, including the development of students' spiritual outlook, beliefs, healthy lifestyle culture, ideological immunity, conceptual foundations for the development of information culture among students were researched by S.Nishonova, U.Aleuov, U.Makhamov, O.Musurmonova, B.Adizov, D.Sharipova, Sh.Sharipov, M.Kuronov, M.Bekmurodov, K.Kuronboyev, O.Jamoliddinova, B.Khodjayev, T.Utebayev, Z.Kurboniyozova, Z.Qosimova and N.M.Dalimova (N.M.Dalimova Features of mental diagnosis and correction aspects of adolescents who are fond of computer games. -T.: 2010.)

Scientists of the CIS countries S.R.Udaloe, S.A.Zaitseva, G.A.Kruchinina, I.A.Bolshakova, O.V.Chernetsova, M.Lapchik, A.A.Mukasheva, R.Y.Hurum, T.A. Lavina (Lavina T.A. To the issue of teacher competency in the field of information and communication technologies in the context of continuous pedagogical education / Chuvash State Pedagogical University Bulletin named after I.Ya.Yakovlev. - 2011. - No.4(72), Part 2.-P.72-75) and others conducted research on the pedagogical and psychological aspects of the formation of the skills of teachers in this area in the formation of information competence of students, foreign experience on the problem. Researchers D.B.Yakubjanova, A.A.Temberbekova (Temberbekova A.A. Information competence of a student of a university as a social pedagogical problem: monograph/A.A.Temberbekova, V.V.Bondar. - M.: MGPU. - 2008. - 193 p.) and others did research on methodological aspects of the formation of information competence in future employees.

Among foreign scientists L.Rogers, J.Tweedle, L.Fernandez-Sans, J.Gomez-Perez, A.Castillo-Martinez, P.B.A.Ojeda, M.F.G.Aguilar, E.S.Zeran (Zeran E.S. Initial teacher training and information and communication technologies at University of Magallanes Chilean Patagonia//Digital Education Review. - 2016. - Issue 30. - P. 135-146) studied the importance of the formation of information and cooperation competencies in future teachers and their use in future pedagogical activities.

An analysis of scientific psychological and pedagogical research in recent years shows that, despite the importance of the direction of the topic under study, there is currently a lack of resources for scientific and practical work on this topic. Indeed, N.I. Sattarova in her research work emphasizes the need to pay attention to the safety of a child using the internet and the author gives a number of recommendations for teachers, students and parents. However, the research focuses only on information security of students in an educational institution and in computer science lessons.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

It is impossible to create an ideal information environment for an effective and full development of the student. “Today our young people receive a variety of information not only in schools, but also through radio and television, the press and the internet. In a world where the global information space is expanding, telling our children not to read it, not see it and surround them with an iron wall, of course, does not meet the requirements of the time and our goals”[4,114].

Indeed, according to this idea, it is completely wrong to surround the reader's mind, to surround it with an iron wall. Perhaps the younger generation needs to enhance one's abilities to withstand and defend against any harmful information.

This means that protecting the younger generation from malicious information threats can be included in the list of global problems that exist in the world today. Since, as mentioned above, as long as there are various threats that negatively affect the upbringing of our children and their negative consequences, the threat of information remains a global problem.

In our investigation of this problem, we have included the following harmful information that negatively affects the physical and mental development of the student:

1. The threat of the spread of mass culture via the internet, telephone, discs.
2. The threat of ideas that contradict different national spirituality.
3. The threat of computer games.
4. Threat of human trafficking.
5. Threats from films promoting militancy, smoking, drug trafficking, etc.

The impact of the negative factors given above can occur for a number of reasons, including:

1. Lack of purposeful organization of student activities.
2. Lack of knowledge about harmful information among students.
3. Lack of measures to protect children from harmful information in the family, educational institutions and communities.
4. Lack of student immunity to the above negative factors, etc.

In order to defend our youngsters from these negative factors we as teachers need to purposefully organize their daily activities; organize an effective cooperation between the family school, the community and the educational institution; we will have to keep them updated on news from the press, theater, television, radio, literature and art, music, sports.

In solving this problem, we need to focus on:

- providing students with knowledge about harmful information and its types, as well as the extent of the negative impact on a person's worldview;
- learning the interests and desires of today's students, appropriately organize work in the direction of their activities;
- identifying the root cause of the problem by learning the current situation in the families and communities of students affected by malicious information;
- developing effective forms of pedagogical education for teachers and parents to protect students from harmful information.

In recent decades, schoolchildren have also become mass consumers of screen art. Actions, thoughts and feelings in them, tricks are depicted in unreal events, and a real person is drawn to imaginary superheroes: violence, cruelty and an emphasis on this violence. Unfortunately, it is precisely these circumstances that make up the major subject of the films.

Today the journalism, particularly television, has a significant impact on how people think consciousness and personality. In modern conditions, from the first months of life, a child finds himself in an environment rich in information: busy parents turn on a video or TV in the evening instead of singing lullaby and fairy tales. The child grows up in a world where the sounds of news, music or movie characters are constantly heard. Television, is one of the most important mediums of mass communication, practically controls culture. Information not presented on TV channels does not affect the state of society.

As digital television and radio broadcasting and internet begins to be used in practice, competition in this part of the market also increased significantly. Children using email freely have access various sites containing harmful information that affects health, mental development and

personal development. As computer technology advances, it becomes easier to view, create, and send multimedia products via e-mail. Children buy cheap uncertified CDs of films and watch them on their computers or TV. The field of information is so vast that it goes beyond management and control.

A small schoolboy, whose worldview is just beginning to form, needs a flow of information in order to carry out social behavior in society.

Cessation of access to information can lead to mental illness or mental imbalance. The child is strongly influenced not only by the constant informative connection with the social environment, but also by the amount, volume, content and structure of incoming and processed information.

I.Gundareva, one of the researchers, believes that the child acquires the necessary knowledge through direct experience, personal dialogue, and a variety of information sources (books, radio, television, computers, magazines, newspapers, symbolic sources). As a result, the majority and large rise in the proportion of information received via information sources or direct experience and personal interaction is the norm of societal progress. [5,17].

Due to the obvious intricacy and dynamism of societal processes, as well as the direct impact of societal changes on a child's daily life, he becomes increasingly reliant on media messages. His everyday encounters may supply him with the information he needs to establish his social character and exist in society. Students can get the most significant social knowledge via television and radio broadcasts, newspapers, and the internet. This is especially evident when it comes to coming up with thoughts about subjects that aren't immediately tied to his personal experience.

Many scientists agree that in today's society, a person's daily existence is reliant on mass communication, which creates a unique "second reality," "subjective reality," that has a bigger impact than objective fact. [3, 26].

The media is one of the most significant socialization organizations in modern society. First and foremost, we are discussing television, which is a practical, ubiquitous, and popular means of reporting and entertainment in this aspect. Today, many researchers believe that television has not only a great, but also a decisive effect on the progression of children and adolescents, their behavior and consciousness. Television is a vital component of culture, spiritual life of a person in the XX-XXI centuries. The media have played a leading role in the leisure time of modern adolescents and have become one of the important agents of socialization.

Thanks to television, at the culmination of the twentieth century, the boundaries between the world of adults and children expanded. The TV screen allows the child to observe the adult world, perceive it and identify with it. Television is a catalyst for social processes and change, responding to important goals.

The ideological and value-normative vacuum in a young person's mentality is brightly filled with "special means" in which the media play an important role. In some cases, the media can cause emotional trauma to the child. Sometimes vivid images of traumatic events, especially of the dead and dying, can in themselves cause traumatic grief for the viewer as real witnesses of the event, which has a detrimental effect on their mental state.

If the perception of a reportage about some terrible event is accompanied by the understanding that the viewer and his or her loved ones can also get into the situation, then the consequences for a person's mental state can last long enough. Of course, this is especially true for children and adolescents with a wide imagination.

Children who watch footage depicting the aftermath of murder and destruction experience horror, sleep disturbances, and panic. For example, a 7-year-old girl woke up in tears and was disappointed after watching a news program, not letting go of her mother for fear of being alone and fearing that something would happen. A 10-year-old boy became depressed after watching videos of actions in "hot spots" and began to expect that "masks (armed men in masks)" would come and kill everyone.

Such changes in children are sometimes observed even after watching the show. The teenager can distinguish real events from feature films, “real” events and “movie events”.

Many scientists around the world are now concerned about the negative consequences of media violence scenes against children. Recently, television violence has also prevailed, with the use of press media and the internet to obtain information about drugs and harmful substances, sectarian groups, pornographic propaganda or other disproportionate information about contemporary negative events.

Modern information technologies have allowed children to use the internet, which is a popular activity along with video games. The experience of the development of open networks around the world, especially the internet, indicates the beginning of a new era in the improvement of data processing systems and tools. The user of such networks perceives himself as an integral part of a single information community and is perceived by others.

One of the negative consequences of the global computer network is the dissemination of various information of dubious content on the network. It's important to note that there are informational effects that directly threaten the mental or physical health of a person. Often such influences form the spiritual and psychological climate in society for several years, creating a criminal environment and leading to an increase in mental illness.

There is a good opportunity for human intelligence to enter a new phase of growth in the creation of a global information space. However, serious scientific research is also needed on this matter, and users of internet services should be informed about its consequences. For example, millions of subscribers - from academics to movie fans - are already online.

At the same time, they include environmentalists, fascist groups and other electronic channels calling for the emergence of ignorance in the new electronic environment. Television using parabolic antennas, video and computers are becoming practically uncontrollable sources of information impact on humans. The result can be an increase in the imbalance under the images of the universe in the imaginations of adults and children [6,35].

The following statement by A.K.Markova is also noteworthy: It is logical to assume that children do not perceive threats in the global network. According to statistics, 9 out of 10 children aged 8 to 15 have been exposed to pornography on the internet, about 17% are regularly connected to prohibited resources, and 5.5% are ready to do what they see [7.36].

Just as it is difficult to predict when a child will accidentally visit a site that recommends the use of drugs and alcohol, explosives, it is impossible to track all the information that goes on the internet.

When a child is working on resources on the web, he is forced to involuntarily see a picture of a body without clothes, which pops up in an advertising window. According to our observations, educators and parents do not understand and do not foresee the dangers posed by the internet. In the meanwhile, the child can participate in satanic rituals of worship, "sex" on the internet, so it is very easy to sit at the computer and attend their meetings. We believe that meeting friends online is a serious risk.

In this case adults can pretend to be teenagers in order to gain the trust of children. A complimenting, benevolent conversation partner engages the child in discussing personal issues and seeks to bond him or her emotionally. Children who feel alienated from their parents are especially vulnerable and do not realize that they have been subjected to evil strategies in this situation [8,71].

According to most parents, children try to access inappropriate sites, download unofficial software, or interact with strangers when they are using the computer, not at school, but mostly at home. The administration of educational institutions uses software that restricts student access to the internet. Due to a lack of parental involvement, the use of the global network by children is not limited [9,134].

Teachers are concerned about the interest of children in mobile phones, and therefore in schools there is an interest in porn and SMS resources that are convenient for accessing the internet from a mobile phone. Critical assessment of pictures or sound images taken from the internet is not typical for children. As a result, students think, "Ringtones are designed by adults, advertised in newspapers, magazines and on television, they can be trusted."

As a result, under the impact of information distribution (mass media, the internet, destructive foreign educational projects), the natural protective mental mechanisms of children are limited, and their ideas about permitted and prohibited, anomalous phenomena disappear. Of course, this is especially true for imaginative children and adolescents. The reader finds himself in the information space created by the mass communications network - a globalized cultural environment and mass media created with the help of new technologies and acting in an information space that combines the socio-cultural significance of various components [10,4].

In this regard, the problem of the structure of values of children as a social agent and the interaction of the information environment arises. This relationship between the environment and the subject is contradictory, which is explained by the complex structure of its components. With the help of this concept, the current sociocultural situation, which determines the characteristics of a child's socialization in a complex information environment, becomes problematic.

The impact of some sources of information varies not just in circumstances with varying substance, but also in terms of social standing and referential status for the learner (the person reporting or advising on specific issues) [10,65].

The student's personality is vulnerable to the influence of various information factors that hinder the observance and formation of purposeful informational foundations of life and social behavior in modern society.

Consequences of the influence of factors of the information environment:

- lack of self-evaluate ;
- inability to adapt to the environment;
- violation of the child's perception of the environment and loss of place in it;
- decreased self-esteem and confidence;
- loss of the idea of "I" and its uniqueness;
- violation of plans and intentions;
- choosing the wrong goals and methods of behavior;
- mental dependence on other subjects of influence;
- violation of morality;
- possible pathological changes in the psyche and mental health disorders.

Thus, damage reflects various levels of imbalance in some mental structures and personality composition, up to the loss of subjectivity and personal stability [11,48].

Thus, the analysis of scientific research and scientific literature shows that the knowledge of students about the threat of malicious information is the need to reduce the consequences of psychological and moral impact, develop skills to counter it, create a modernized system, or, in particular, in other words, a pedagogically oriented process.

5.CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of theoretical and practical research, the following conclusions were drawn about protecting students from the threat of malicious information:

1. Protecting students from the threat of malicious information should be organized in the school-district-family system and there should be a strong link between these systems.

2. It is required to improve effective use strategies of the pedagogical potential of humane education, reflected in national and universal values, in protecting primary schoolchildren from the threat of harmful information.

3. The effective organization of students' free time, especially the acquaintance with a faithful friend, like a book, is a reliable factor in protecting against harmful information.

4. It is necessary to improve the system of training future primary school teachers for educational activities in higher educational institutions and, in particular, pay special attention to their proficiency in methods and means of protecting students from malicious information.

5. Parents should be given pedagogical knowledge to protect students from harmful information. This is because parental involvement is also important in overcoming this problem.

On the basis of the above principles, it is necessary to give several ways to solve this urgent problem:

1. A way to justify the activities of all types of media through legislation as a way to protect children from harmful information.

2. Introduce the course of media education into the curricula of general educational institutions of secondary education.

3. Regular formation of students' independent and critical thinking in the process of studying all academic disciplines.

4. Teach students to resist various information threats and form ideological immunity.

Without legal regulation of the media, it is difficult to solve the issue of eliminating the threat of harmful information to citizens, especially students. However, this requires an assessment and understanding of the information offered. The role of the education system and the family is important. In particular, it is advisable to pay particular attention, in other words, concentrate fully to the field of science - media education, that is, the study of various media, primarily television, radio, press, the specific language of the internet, that is, to create reflection, immunity to the objective evaluation of the information offered.

In order not to be tied to information, you must first pay attention to the source of the information. It is vital to make certain, that the information provided is true (scientific, spiritual, cultural), accurate (including historical). For this, the acquisition of knowledge, teaching the ability to compare the proposed information with the previously known and selectively receiving information is an important pedagogical task. In this regard, motivational, adaptive, psychological and psychological characteristics of protecting students from the threat of harmful information were selected depending on ensuring rational harmony of consciousness-cognition-emotion, systematization of close adults and social factors.

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